

**THOUGHTS OF THE THINKER AND EDUCATOR ABDULLAH
AVLANI ABOUT EDUCATION**

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Abstract: In this article, Abdullah Avlani glorified the culture of world peoples, science, school and education in his works, called on people to be educated and cultural, saying that morality is a set of behavior patterns and it is necessary to look at the upbringing of children. . shot By studying the opinions of scientists, the moral and educational qualities characteristic of our people were touched upon, as well as the example of the early education of our parents, sincere attitude and excellent behavior in the family.

Key words: culture, science, school and education, knowledgeable, ethics, behavior. child, education, virtue, relationships, family.

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Issues such as child development, education, health promotion, national values, love for the Motherland. When he grew up, the “Education” of the thinker Abdullah Awlani is for us either life - or death, or salvation - or death, or happiness - or This is a disaster - his meaningful thoughts. we understand that this is true. It was the educational center of the family - a sacred place that preserves the continuity of each people, ensures the development of national values, is a means of giving birth and raising a physically healthy generation, educating patriotic defenders of this country. A person receives his first education from his family, from the heart of love, mother's milk and his own milk. His influence was firmly established in nature and in the human heart. a child is formed in every

family on the basis of internal, certain laws of perfection, spirit, kindness and decency. As the President noted: “It is clear to all of us that every person belongs to every family in our country. the best dreams and goals, life interests, first of all, are manifested and realized in the image of their children”³. This is also a matter of spiritual education of children. it is important. When we look at the upbringing of the children of thinkers and study the thoughts of scientists, the moral and educational qualities of our people are involuntarily embodied before our eyes. And also an example of the early education of our parents, sincere attitude and good behavior in the family.

Main part

The famous teacher, talented poet and teacher Abdullah Avloni was born on July 12, 1878 in Tashkent into a peasant family and studied at the old school. He wrote about this in his autobiography: “I started studying at the Okchinsky district madrasah at the age of 12. From the age of 13, he worked in the summer to help his family and studied in the winter. From the age of 14 I began to write various poems of that time. At that time, I read the Tarjumon newspaper and became aware of the times. Avloni graduated from a madrasah and became a school teacher. He reformed the method of teaching and learning, founded a new type of school, carried out important educational work such as imparting modern knowledge to young student teachers, teaching Eastern and Western languages. He wrote such textbooks as “The First Teacher”, “The Second Teacher” (1912), “Tarikh”, “Turkish Gulistan Yahud Ahlok” (1913), which were a phenomenon for their time. Avloni, who began his creative activity in 1895, created poems, stories, feuilletons and small dramatic works under the pseudonyms “Kabin”, “Shukhrat”, “Hijran”, “Avloni”, “Surayo”, “Abulfayz”, “Indamas”... In his works the poet criticizes backwardness and ignorance of his time and calls people to enlightenment. The thinker, teacher Abdullah Avlani made a great contribution to the development of education. A teacher who embodies in his work the best

traditions of our people, a creator, publisher and public figure. Abdullah Avlani is a “usuli jadid”, that is, schools with advanced methods: “Literature or folk poetry,” “The First Teacher,” “Türk Gulistani, or Ethics,” “The Second Teacher,” “School.” He created textbooks and textbooks like “Gulistoni.”

The famous and famous Abdullah Avlani in his works glorified the culture of the world's peoples, science, school and education, including Quranic suras, hadiths, the rich pedagogical heritage of the Uzbek people - fairy tales, proverbs, riddles and didactic stories. These books use words that encourage people to be educated and cultured. According to the thinker, morality is a set of patterns of behavior. Behavior and kindness in a particular person or the manifestation of evil is a form of existence. Abdullah Avloni in his work “Turkish Gulistan or Morality” describes the education of children in four areas:

It is enough to divide it into sections such as “Teaching time”, “Physical education”, “Education of thinking”, “Ethical education”. The Time of Education section states that education should begin from the day the child is born. “Education Who does this?”, “How is this done?” rushes into the midst of questions and seeks answers to them. “First of all, this is home education. This is a mother's duty. Secondly, the assessment of schools and madrassas is the responsibility of the father, teacher, teacher and the state,” it is emphasized that education is the responsibility of every person - parents, teachers, the state and others. These words of the great enlightener were important and relevant for our people at the beginning of our century. it is equally important and relevant for us today. Because education

- a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is a factor determining the level of consciousness and its development. Therefore, it is impossible to change consciousness without changing the education system. And without changing our opinions and thinking, we will not be able to build a free and prosperous society.

As we see, all these issues are closely related to each other, like a chain," he said

earlier. His thoughts and comments are of great value attached to the work of Abdullah Avloni. Education is not a personal issue, but a national issue. It is a social work. The development of each nation and the power of its states are too great for the education of generations. Thanks to this, Abdullah Avloni was the first among Uzbek intellectuals who paid great attention to the education of children. Allama's education is national, not private. I conclude that it is a social work will come. Avloni was the only one who understood education in a broad sense and was not limited to moral education. First of all, he focuses on the need to take care of the health of his child. According to Avloni, in order to have a healthy soul, good morals and knowledge, you must first of all be physically healthy. As Avloni noted, "a person owns a healthy and strong part of the body." this is the most desirable thing. Because a person needs strength and a healthy body to study, teach, study and teach. Physical education, children's health Abdullah Avloni Addressing parents, he emphasizes that the main responsibility for education lies with teachers. Development of children's thinking abilities Formation of a worldview is a sacred duty entrusted to the "attention and conscience" of the teacher... After all, strength, beauty, breadth of thought is service to the teacher. it depends on his upbringing and training," says the teacher. At the same time, thinker Abdullah Avloni: "Education and learning are interconnected processes; there is a slight difference between lessons and learning, even if this is true. separated from each other: "The body is like a body with a soul enriched by it," he says. He expresses a strong opinion that knowledge is the only good and benefit for man. Only in a person brought up in the spirit of science and noble ideas, a sense of the Motherland is formed, love for the Motherland is awakened, and loyalty is allowed. This shows that without these qualities it is impossible to imagine an ideal person. The development of a country depends, first of all, on its children, their spiritual and physical maturity. Therefore, Abdullah Avloni is a book for young people, designed to acquire

knowledge and useful skills. Raising children in the spirit of the spiritual heritage of Eastern thinkers encourages them to study. Avlani also equates ignorance with ignorance and expresses the following thoughts: “Ignorance refers to the uneducated, the uneducated and the ignorant,” he says. “Science is a friend in the desert, life is a support on the roads. In lonely moments - a friend, in happy moments - a leader, in sad moments - an assistant between people.” “zebu zinat, a weapon in the fight against enemies.” The Thinker said: “Beauty is not in the face, brother.” Everyone likes good people,” he addressed the people. Our words encourage us to be kind so that we can be an example for our children.

Summary.

As we all know, the holy book and our values, the legacy of the great thinkers of the East, always force us to live by honest work, courage, generosity and generosity, call us to humility, justice and kindness. Of course, it is impossible to imagine unique customs and traditions without spirituality, history and national values. If parents are satisfied, we can conclude that education is today, tomorrow and the future of the child. This is why education is a social phenomenon. Education has existed since the beginning of human society. after all, in order for a person to be the most perfect species on earth, he must first of all be educated. Although the work has been written for almost a century, it has not lost its value. Our people have a saying: “A teacher must first of all be knowledgeable.” It is the duty of each of us to use the thoughts, advice and wisdom of thinkers in raising children, expanding and enriching their spiritual horizons, and raising an ideal person.

Books:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. Humanity, kindness and creativity are the main foundations of our national idea. Tashkent, 2021.
2. Mirziyoyev Sh.M. June 24, 2017 "Khalk Sozi" newspaper
3. Karimov I. High spirituality is an indomitable force. Tashkent. // “Spirituality”

- 2008. P. 62.

4. Mardonov Sh.K. Development of technology for an electronic module of didactic support in pedagogy.-T. "Reliable partner".2021,54-60b.

5. Abduzhalilova Sh. “The concept of pedagogical education in the family in the works of Abdurauf Fitrat.” p-ISSN: 26153785 I Volume 5, Issue 1, January 2022

6. The personality of the teacher as a factor in the effectiveness of pedagogical communication. Journal of interdisciplinary innovation and scientific research in Uzbekistan No. 9 06.20.2022173-177b Treasury of proverbs. Collector: M. Azamatov. Compiler of glossary and annotations: Naim Norkulov. T., 1977. S. 18, 30, 44.

7. P. Taranov. Encyclopedia of Higher Intelligence. M., 1999. B-16.